

ISic3104

I.Sicily inscription 3104

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331430

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. [— —] ὑπ (ατία) Πα [υλίνου]
3. [μηνί] Ὀκτωβρ [ίω ταῖς —]
- 4.
5. [— —] ὑπ (ατία) Πα[υλίνου πρ(ὸ) —' καλ]-
6. [ανδῶν] Ὀκτωβρ [ίων ἡμέρα —]
- 7.
8. [— —] ὑπ (ατία) Πα [υλίνου νέου]
9. [μηνί] Ὀκτωβρ [ίω ταῖς —]
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645452

PHI 331430

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0882

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 24 no.77 fig.2c and 14 no.42

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